

Supplementary Materials

Supplementary Figure 1

Snapshots of time-series recordings of hemodynamic variables from coronary microembolization to completion of measurements in all animals (n = 5) in the heart failure (HF) model are shown. This figure is provided as a reference to clarify the temporal context from coronary microembolization to the initiation of hemodynamic measurements. Symbols indicate the timing of coronary microembolization (◆), the start of baseline measurements (△), and the initiation of milrinone infusion (○).

Supplementary Figure 2

Hemodynamic effects of milrinone in the normal model group. Panels **A–N** present the milrinone-induced changes in heart rate (HR), arterial pressure (AP), pulmonary arterial pressure (PAP), left atrial pressure (LAP), right atrial pressure (RAP), aortic flow (AoF), stroke volume (SV), stressed blood volume (SBV), systemic vascular resistance (SVR), pulmonary vascular resistance (PVR), pulmonary arterial pulsatility index (PAPI), end-systolic elastance (E_{es}), effective arterial elastance (E_a), and the logarithmic slope of the cardiac output curve (SL), respectively. Box-and-whisker plots display the median (horizontal line), 25th–75th percentiles (box), and minimum and maximum values (whiskers). Dashed lines connect the data from paired observations in the same animals ($n = 5$). Statistical analyses were performed using the Friedman test with post hoc Dunn's test against baseline for simultaneous multiple comparisons. P values from the Friedman test (upper-right corner) or P-value from Dunn's test (baseline vs. each condition) is shown within each panel. Differences were considered statistically significant when $P < 0.05$.

Supplementary Figure 3

Hemodynamic effects of milrinone in the heart failure model group. The panels, data presentation, and statistical methods are the same as in Supplementary Figure 2.

Supplementary Figure 4

Comparison of the hemodynamic effects of milrinone at $0.5 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ between the normal and heart failure (HF) models. Absolute values of heart rate (HR), arterial pressure (AP), pulmonary artery pressure (PAP), left atrial pressure (LAP), right atrial pressure (RAP), aortic flow (AoF), stroke volume (SV), stressed blood volume (SBV), systemic vascular resistance (SVR), pulmonary vascular resistance (PVR), pulmonary artery pulsatility index (PAPI), end-systolic elastance (E_{es}), effective arterial elastance (E_a), and the slope of the left ventricular output curve (SL) at baseline (BL) and during milrinone infusion at $0.5 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ in the normal and HF models are shown as box-and-whisker plots. Dashed lines connect paired observations obtained from the same animals (normal model, $n = 5$; HF model, $n = 5$). Data were analyzed using a nonparametric two-way analysis of variance based on the aligned rank transform (ART), with model (normal vs. HF) as a between-group factor and drug (baseline vs. milrinone) as a within-group (repeated-measures) factor. The main effects of model and drug, as well as the model \times drug interaction, are indicated for each variable. When significant main effects or interactions were detected, post hoc comparisons were performed using the Mann–Whitney U test (between models) and the Wilcoxon signed-rank test (within the same animals), with P values adjusted using Holm’s method. * and ** indicate statistical significance at $P < 0.05$ and $P < 0.01$, respectively.

Supplementary Figure 5

A) Canine 1

B) Canine 2

C) Canine 3

Hemodynamics of the acute ischemic heart failure (HF) model with intact baroreflex and vagal nerves. **A)–C)** Snapshots of raw hemodynamic recordings obtained from three dogs with acute ischemic HF under intact baroreflex and vagal nerve conditions. The black rectangles indicate the time windows during which hemodynamic data were collected according to the experimental protocol. **D)** Summary of hemodynamic variables in the HF model with intact baroreflex and vagal nerves. Data are shown as mean \pm SD ($n = 3$), with gray lines connecting repeated measurements within the same animal. Statistical analysis was not performed due to the small sample size. HR, heart rate; AP, arterial pressure; PAP, pulmonary arterial pressure; LAP, left atrial pressure; RAP, right atrial pressure; AoF, aortic flow; SV, stroke volume; SBV, stressed blood volume; SVR, systemic vascular resistance; PVR, pulmonary vascular resistance; PAPI, pulmonary artery pulsatility index; E_{es} , end-systolic elastance; E_a , effective arterial elastance; SL, the slope of the left ventricular output curve.

Supplementary Table 1. Hemodynamic variables used for constructing Figure 7

	Baseline	During milrinone infusion
Normal		
LAP, mmHg	7.4	5.6
RAP, mmHg	3.5	2.9
CO, mL·min ⁻¹ ·kg ⁻¹	150.9	128.6
SBV, mL/kg	31.6	26.5
SR, mL·min ⁻¹ ·kg ⁻¹	76.0	71.1
SL, mL·min ⁻¹ ·kg ⁻¹	61.6	62.2
Heart Failure		
LAP, mmHg	19.6	13.0
RAP, mmHg	7.4	5.9
CO, mL·min ⁻¹ ·kg ⁻¹	65.0	89.5
SBV, mL/kg	35.7	32.1
SR, mL·min ⁻¹ ·kg ⁻¹	27.1	35.0
SL, mL·min ⁻¹ ·kg ⁻¹	18.3	30.2

LAP, left atrial pressure; RAP, right atrial pressure; CO, cardiac output; SBV, stressed blood volume; SR, logarithmic slope of the right ventricular cardiac output curve; SL, logarithmic slope of the left ventricular cardiac output curve. Values represent mean data obtained from five animals in each group. Data during milrinone infusion were obtained at a dose of 0.5 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$. CO was measured as aortic flow (AoF) and is expressed per unit body weight ($\text{mL}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$). SR was calculated from $\text{CO}_R = \text{SR} \{ \log(\text{RAP} - 2.13) + 1.9 \} (1)$. When RAP was < 2.13 mmHg, the logarithmic term became undefined. In the normal model, RAP was < 2.13 mmHg in two animals. Therefore, SR values for the normal model were calculated as the mean of the remaining three animals.

Supplementary Table 2. Hemodynamic variables used for constructing Figure 8

	Baseline	During milrinone infusion
Group I		
LAP, mmHg	25.0	12.0
RAP, mmHg	6.0	4.0
CO, mL·min ⁻¹ ·kg ⁻¹	54.2	62.3
SBV, mL/kg	33.4	23.6
SR, mL·min ⁻¹ ·kg ⁻¹	16.7	24.7
SL, mL·min ⁻¹ ·kg ⁻¹	13.8	22.1
Group II		
LAP, mmHg	10.0	4.0
RAP, mmHg	2.0	1.6
CO, mL·min ⁻¹ ·kg ⁻¹	65.0	57.0
SBV, mL/kg	18	13.2
SR, mL·min ⁻¹ ·kg ⁻¹	36.9*	32.4*
SL, mL·min ⁻¹ ·kg ⁻¹	22.6	38.6

LAP, left atrial pressure; RAP, right atrial pressure; CO, cardiac output; SBV, stressed blood volume; SR, logarithmic slope of the right ventricular cardiac output curve; SL, logarithmic slope of the left ventricular cardiac output curve. Hemodynamic data for LAP, RAP, and cardiac index (CI) were extracted from Table 2 and Figure 4 of Remme et al. (2). Because individual patient data on height, body weight, or body surface area (BSA) were not reported in the original article, anthropometric parameters were estimated based on cohort-based data for Dutch individuals born in 1930, as reported by Statistics Netherlands (CBS) (3). Body mass index was assumed to be 22. Based on these assumptions, the mean body size of a mixed-sex cohort consisting of 12 men and 6 women was estimated as a height of 172.2 cm, body weight of 65.3 kg, and BSA of 1.77 m², calculated using the Du Bois formula. CO was calculated from the reported cardiac index and the estimated body surface area. SBV was calculated by substituting LAP, RAP, and CO into Equation 2 described in the original manuscript. SL was calculated using Equation 3, and SR was calculated from $CO_R = SR \{ \log(RAP - 2.13) + 1.9 \}$ (1). When RAP was < 2.13 mmHg, as observed in Group II, the logarithmic term became undefined, precluding direct calculation of SR. To allow estimation of SR for these conditions, RAP was fixed at 3 mmHg as a lower bound, and the resulting SR values are marked with an asterisk (*).

References

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3. Statistics Netherlands (CBS). How tall are Dutch people? The Netherlands in Numbers. 2021. [Online]. <https://longreads.cbs.nl/the-netherlands-in-numbers-2021/how-tall-are-dutch-people/> [15 Jan. 2026].